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TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER EXPERIENCES AND FUTURE CHALLENGES IN AUGMENTED HUMANS TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the knowledge and trends in articles about technology transfer experiences and future challenges within the scope of Augmented Human Technologies in the literature. The research method adopted for this study is a systematic review (meta-synthesis). The literature was scanned using a series of keywords related to the concepts of Augmented Human and technology transfer experiences, limiting open access publications. The study sheds light on the challenges and opportunities in integrating advanced technologies to augment human capabilities, addressing both technical and ethical considerations. The diverse range of topics covered in this study lays the foundation for understanding the interdisciplinary nature of research in this domain and the potential for future advancements in augmented human technologies.

Keywords: Augmented Human, Technology Transfer, Ethical Concerns, Systematic Review, Meta-synthesis.